

here: Appendix for the Application of Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc for Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK), Research Fellowship for Foreign Citizens (Code 2216) for the research stay at the Eurasia Institute of Earth Sciences, Istanbul Technical University

duration: Two months, from the 01st of May 2012 until the 30th of June 2012

Research Plan

for the research stay of the visiting researcher Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc in *Eurasia Institute of Earth Sciences* of the *Istanbul Technical University*, in the time span of 01st May 2012 - 30th June 2012, under the supervision of Prof. Dr. H. Nüzhet Dalfes.

Research topic: **Adaptation of ecosystems to climate change: Anatolian Plateau, Turkey.**

Research area: **Anatolian Plateau, Turkey (Eastern part):**

Southeastern Anatolia, Central Anatolia, Eastern Anatolia.

The most important regional areas (focus of the research): Eastern Taurus Mountains; Pontic Mountains (Kaçkars); East Anatolian Plateau.

Research questions:

- 1) Did the landscapes in eastern Turkey changed over the past 20 years ?
If “yes”, demonstrate changes on maps (“earlier” and “nowadays”).
- 2) What are the dominating land cover types in the landscapes ?
Visualize on map: “Land cover types in eastern Anatolian Plateau, Turkey”.

Research main steps: 1) Spatial analysis of land cover types in Eastern Anatolian Plateau
2) Environmental mapping of mountainous landscapes
3) One (1) publication of the research results in a scientific journal
or one (1) poster for presentation at upcoming geosciences conference

Expected results:

- ✓ Analysis of the landscape changes in Anatolian Plateau (Eastern part):
Southeastern Anatolia, Central & Eastern Anatolia
- ✓ Thematic map of the land cover types in Eastern Anatolian Plateau
- ✓ Report for the TÜBİTAK resuming results of the research work
- ✓ An article reporting the outcome of the research work published in peer-reviewed journal (environment or earth sciences) **or** poster for presentation on a geoscience conference

Research GIS data:

Data collecting is suggested to be prepared in advance, before starting research in Istanbul, because the geodata that will be used are available in the free internet access on the web. GIS open source-based geodata will be used for the analysis of the landscape changes in eastern Turkey. These include aerial and satellite imagery covering different time period (time span of 10-20 years). The sources for these geodata include the following types:

- ✓ Satellite imagery from various sources, e.g. USGS (<http://www.usgs.gov/pubprod/>), The Earth Science Data Interface (<http://glcfapp.glc.f.umd.edu/>), GloVis (<http://glovis.usgs.gov/>)
- ✓ free Digital Elevation Models for relief modelling, from the open source <http://geomorphometry.org/content/data-sets> or ASTER GDEM <http://www.gdem.aster.ersdac.or.jp/search.jsp>
- ✓ Aerial imagery from the Google Earth server (earth.google.com)

Technical background: The research will be technically based on following open source GIS software: *Quantum GIS*, *ILWIS* for raster processing and geodata modelling. The *ArcGIS* can be used as well (depending on license availability).

Detailed research plan (scheduled on two-week periods)

§ 1. **01 May – 15 May: Data organizing, starting GIS project**

The first, initial part of the research working plan includes:

- ▲ organizing previously collected geodata on the *Institute's* computer (on hard disk),
- ▲ discussing, overviewing and assessment of these materials with supervisor (Prof. Dr. N. Dalfes) and colleagues in order to become familiar with all available resources
- ▲ starting GIS project, geo-referencing (if necessary), organizing geodata in ArcGIS / ILWIS

§ 2. **15 May – 01 June: Spatial analysis in GIS project**

- ▲ Spatial analysis of the thematic layers. Spatial analysis of the geodata is aimed to perform physical-geographical overview and landscapes of the Anatolian Plateau and to analyze distribution of various land use types over regions of Eastern Turkey
- ▲ Preparing thematic layers in *ArcGIS* and/or *ILWIS*: Geomorphological relief of Eastern Anatolia & Taurus mountains, based on DEM and Landscapes and land cover types in Eastern Anatolia
- ▲ Performing image processing using supervised classification (ILWIS) for indication of land cover types in the Anatolian Plateau and Eastern Taurus mountains
- ▲ Environmental change detection: overlay of the geodata (aerial photographs, DEMs and satellite images) using cartographic methods, to compare changes in landscape patterns at present and 10-20 years ago (time span 1990 – 2010).

§ 3. **01 June – 15 June: Thematic mapping: land cover types in Anatolian Plateau**

- Regional studies of East Anatolian Plateau: land cover types & landscape patterns
- Creating thematic maps detecting landscape dynamics since 1990
- Creating thematic maps demonstrating land cover types over the research area.

§ 4. **15 June – 30 June: Preparing final report writing paper for publication**

1. Writing article for the publication in a scientific journal: “*Environmental changes in mountainous landscapes: Anatolian Plateau, Turkey*”.
2. Preparing final report for the TÜBİTAK, Ankara.

16th of August, 2011.

Scientific supervisor:
Prof. Dr. H. Nüzhet DALFES

Visiting researcher:
Polina Lemenkova, M.Sc